

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PROBLEM BASED LEARNING IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT: Modern employers need specialists who are not just well experienced in the relevant field, but have the skills to apply the acquired knowledge in solving everyday productive tasks. This forces higher education teachers to restructure the educational process in particular teaching methods we settled on the methodology of problem-based learning. This article purposes to describe this topic and introduce some steps to create teacher and learners roles in problem-based learning and learning strategies in foreign language classes.

Key words: problem-based learning, students approach, usage, foreign languages, class.

INTRODUCTION

Language is a tool for communication and in order to communicate effectively. Also a good command of reading, writing, listening and speaking is fundamental. Today, millions of people want to improve their command of English as it is still the most important international language in the world. Learning in foreign languages sometimes can create some problems based in your studies. But there are several ways of solving methods which aims to develop problem solving skills in order to fixed easily in our learning environment. That's why some methods are useful to use in this ways.

H. Barrows characterizes this methods of teaching as follows: 1) it is focused on the student's personality; 2) at the center of the learning process is a specific problem that needs to be solved; 3) it is aimed at working in small groups under the supervision of a teacher coordinator [1]. Using these kind of methods are help to improve knowledge of learning foreign languages. When developing materials for work in the classroom we followed the generally accepted three level system of this methods: theory, model, practice.

Materials and methods. Provided that students have a certain basic level of foreign language proficiency, feel comfortable in the learning environment and they are sufficiently motivated by their parents and teachers. The implementation of educational activities based on problem solving begins with presentation of relevant problem. The task of presenting a problem is to stimulate student's need to solve it. To do this, it is proposed to use documentaries, collections of newspaper publications, introductory practice or presentation by a specialist in this field [2].

Also it is important to motivate the students in such a way that is help to achieving their goals easily. In general, tasks aim at solving the problem were offered to students, study in the foundation of additional or professional education under a program and were used in classes on the practice of a foreign language in professional communication namely.

Results and discussion. Some materials on foreign language of professional communication should integrate language material on a foreign language. The content related to professional activity. The successful integration of the language and the content of specialized disciplines in foreign language classes of professional communication should fulfill the tasks of language teaching. The training professional skills, as well as provide opportunities for improving foreign language proficiency and for professional growth.

It is believed that within the framework of higher education, language proficiency and professional knowledge should be developed simultaneously. In foreign language classes you should rely on scientific materials related to the main disciplines that developing professional skills. The integration of language material and professionally oriented learning provides a tool with which students can continue to develop their scientific knowledge and cognitive skills simultaneously with increasing the level of proficiency in foreign languages [3].

The role of teacher at the learning process. Teachers are play most important role in order to increase the knowledge of students in learning areas. They give a help to flourishing students knowledge of learning in foreign languages. The task of a teacher in problem oriented teaching is as follows:

- to identify a problem that is quite complex and unclear, but at the same time arousing interest among students. It should be related to the content of the main course in the specialty. At the same time, the task of solving the problem should contribute to the capture of new skills;
- organizing some groups of trainee with different skill levels in order to achieve greater results in the groups. To do this trainees must identify their strengths and weaknesses which will help in the distribution of roles during the team problem solving process.

The tasks of students during the lessons. While problem-solving training, students collaborate in small groups to study and then solve the proposed problem. As students study problem it is expected that students will fill in the gaps in knowledge and lack of skills, solve, what information do they still to get in order to cope with the task.

The following are the stages that trainees go through in the process of solving a problem situation.

Trainee:

- studies issues related to the problem situation, reads, discusses, and analyzes the problem in the groups, highlighting it is main parts;
- makes a list of what he\she knows about the problem, discusses his\her knowledge in the team with the help of teacher;
- develops and prescribes the problem statement in his own word: it should be based on what the learner knows about the problem and what needs to be learned to solve the task.
- makes a list of actions to be taken according to the schedule, answering the following questions:
 - a) what we need to know and do to solve the problem;
 - b) how to prioritize these actions;
 - c) how do these actions relate to the list of possible solutions to the given problem;
 - d) does the team agree with such actions and if not how to come to a consensus [4].

Summing up the results of potential increase the motivation of students is always give huge results in their study. Increases the level of their professional competences the use of a foreign language when performing everyday professional tasks. This is turn increase their competitiveness in their learning areas.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the implementation of problem-based learning in a foreign language learning environment offers numerous benefits for students. By engaging in real world problems and challenges, students have the opportunity to develop their language skills in a meaningful context. This method promotes collaborative learning, language immersion and the

integration of all language skills, allowing students to practice speaking, listening, reading and writing in the target language. Also, foreign language learning environment can enhance student's language skills, promote meaningful learning experiences and prepare them for real world communication and interaction in the language learning sphere.

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